

CHRISTIAN CLERICS AND POLITICAL GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA: A HISTORICAL REVIEW

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Abstract

Nigeria is one of the most populous countries in Africa with diverse religious practices. The constitution of Nigeria recognizes three major religions, viz, Traditional Religion, Christianity, and Islam. These religions have aligned themselves with political activities. In Nigeria, politics is said to be a dirty game, and a Christian is supposed to be a holy person; therefore, Christian Clerics' participation in democratic governance has always been controversial. Nigerian society needs to be led by good people who have zero tolerance for corruption. Christians cannot achieve much without being involved in partisan politics. Adopting the historical method, this paper explores the ways in which Christian Clerics in Nigeria have contributed to and can continue to contribute to governance in Nigeria. The paper finds that lack of theological education and lack of unity in the body of Christ appear to be some of the misconceptions surrounding Christian Clerics' involvement in politics. The lips of the clergy must keep knowledge and passionately present the gospel to secure the people's hearts for Christ. These are some of the roles of Christian clerics in Nigeria's democratic governance. The paper concludes and recommends that the source of bad political governance should thus be attacked at the root, and Christian Clerics' participation in Nigerian politics is indispensable.

Keywords: Christian, Clerics, Politics, Governance, and Nigeria.

Introduction

African Countries have passed through various forms of government. In many countries on this Continent, generally and Nigeria specifically, before the advent of the colonial era, people were ruled by Kings (Obas), Chiefs (Báálè) in Yorùbá lands, and Emirs, Magají, or *Alángúá* in Hausa lands. These were the hereditary monarchies (Bodunrin, 4). On January 1, 1914, the British Protectorates of Northern and Southern Nigeria were formally amalgamated into a single geopolitical entity by Sir Frederick Lugard. However, Turaki (2017:196) confirms that the two protectorates were administered separately. Miss Flora Shaw (later Lady Lugard) had suggested, as early as 1898, the naming of the British Protectorates on the Niger as Nigeria (Ajayi, 2017). This means the nation that

came into being was, and still is, a conglomeration of ethnic nationalities, with varied cultures and religions.

Religion is present in almost all aspects of human life, and it has shaped the social, cultural, economic, and political affairs of its adherents. The mutual relationship between religion and politics continued in Nigeria with the entrance of Christianity and Islam into the Country (Folarin, 2012), especially as both religions were universal. The successful introduction of Christianity and Islam affected politics and political culture, as ideas were drawn from both religions. The Nigerian Constitution allows room and avenues for freedom of religion. Without undue harassment, every Nigerian has the right to change their religious views and beliefs.

Christian Clerics may be described as ordained priests or ministers in Christian churches. Persons in any of the “five-fold offices” identified in the book of Ephesians 4:11 as Apostles, Prophets, Evangelists, Pastors, and Teachers are all Clerics. It can be argued that holders of these offices can, to some extent, contribute to political governance in Nigeria without being unduly apologetic (Adekunle, 2019). This fact can be established from the Bible and in the history of the Church.

Christianity, Politics, and Governance

Christianity is one of the significant religions recognised in the Nigerian constitution, although the Country is under a democratic government with a secular constitution and the rule of law (Falola, 2018). However, it is unfortunate that some members of the body of Christ see politics and governance as things of this world. This is because the early church dealt with matters of doctrine, discipline, and liturgy mostly ecclesiastically (Boer, 2003). The state had no say or representation in the affairs of the Christian church. Many of the Western Christian societies in Africa then advocated for strict separation between the Church and the State. Among these missions was that of the Mennonites, which metamorphosed into the United Missionary Church of Africa, and they believed that Christians should not participate in civil government (Oyeku, 40). These Canadian and North American missionaries insisted that the Church was to be seen as entirely different from the State. To these missionaries, pastors were forbidden to have anything to do with politics because it was deemed dirty and worldly (Oyeku, 41). Presently in Nigeria, security challenges have caused several human deaths, economic downturn, spates of religious/congregational meetings that have, in turn, led to disrupted social life, health, and insecurity. These have led to adverse effects on the Church and national development of the country (Baiyeshea, 2023). Baiyeshea further corroborates insecurity in Nigeria as evident in a series of emotional, physical, economic, psychological, health, and sexual abuses in the country (2023). It is sufficient to say that the church has not been

exempt from these various insecurities in the country. The standard of education in this nation has almost collapsed. The number of university graduates without jobs is increasing every year. Factories and companies are relocating to neighbouring countries where there is a constant supply of energy. Unemployment is always on the increase, and Nigeria has become the capital of poverty in the world. Hunger and hardship are almost everywhere in Nigeria. Should Christian clergy continue to fold their hands and feel unconcerned in the present state of Nigeria?

Tribal Regions of 1946 and Nigeria's First Republic (1960-65)

Nigeria comprises people of diverse nationalities, ethnic groups, and religions, all of whom have equal stakes in the country. The Nation is an amalgamation of various peoples with diverse identities and differing religious backgrounds and orientations. These were recognised in the formulation of various constitutions that the country has had before and after its independence on October 1, 1960. The various constitutions of Nigeria include: Order in Council over Crown Colony in 1913, Clifford Constitution 1922, Richard Constitution in 1946, Macpherson Constitution in 1951, Lyttleton Constitution 1954, Westminster Constitution 1946, first Constitution upon Independence approved by British Order in 1960, second Post- Independence Constitution 1963, until the first Military Coup, when the 1979 Constitution changed to American Presidential System; 1993 Constitution under oversight of the Military and the 1999 Constitution, also produced by the Military (Asaju, 2023).

In 1946, the British government introduced the Richards constitution, which broke up Nigeria into three major regions of the North, West, and East. This came into being as a result of the fear of the political and patriotic activities of the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC), then led by Sir Herbert Macaulay. The British feared that a strong, united, and national front of Nigerians would pose a serious problem to their colonial rule in Nigeria. Therefore, the response from London was the immediate breakup of Nigeria into tribal regions (Olatunde, 2005). In December 1949, the Northern People's Congress (NPC) was founded under the leadership of Sir Ahmadu Bello. The party later formed the government of the Northern region. This party won the largest number of seats in the 1959 General Elections and formed a coalition government with the NCNC. Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa of the NPC then became the Governor-General (Olatunde, 2005).

The Action Group (AG) was also formed in Ibadan in March 1950, and in 1951, was formally inaugurated in Owo, the present Ondo State. In 1945, the party began as 'Egbé Ọmọ Ọ̀dùduwà' (Association of Ọ̀dùduwà). It functioned until 1948, when it was introduced into Nigeria as a cultural organisation, primarily for the benefit of the Yorùbá. Chief Jeremiah Obafemi Awolowo became Premier of the Western region (Olatunde, 2005). During this period, the Nation was characterised by moves toward regional autonomy. Thus, there was no political

tension in Nigeria that could prompt Christian Clerics to speak out on the nation's political governance.

Nigeria's Second Republic (1979-1983): Nigeria started a new democratic experiment on October 1, 1979. The Presidential Constitution of 1979 attempted to establish a more unified constitutional framework by making the country a single constituency for the president and by removing institutionalised opposition to the governing power. Furthermore, the separation of the three branches of government (Executive, Legislature, and Judiciary), unlike what prevailed in previous constitutions, and the granting of certain constitutional powers to the legislature were intended to prevent the arbitrary use of power by the president or any governing body (Ajayi, 2017). After four years of civilian rule from 1979 to 1983, the Nigerian military seized power on December 31, 1983, and remained in power until 1999. During this period, there were campaigns in various ways in churches at different times, but the voice of Christian clerics was not heard coming out to be voted for. There were seven presidential contestants; the only Christian among them was Joseph Tarka, who lost to Alhaji Sheu Shagari in 1999.

Nigeria's Third Republic: The Third Republic did not exist. The Federal Republic of Nigeria had voted Chief Moshood Kasimawo Olawale Abiola, who won the June 12, 1993, presidential election. Still, the election was annulled by former military Head of State Major General Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida, who subsequently made himself the Military President. However, towards the end of his first term in 2019, President Muhammadu Buhari recognised and declared June 12 a national public holiday in recognition of democracy. The abortion of the Third Republic is the starting point for understanding the elections that led to the Fourth Republic. During this period, the country was about returning to a democratic system of government, and there was peace in the Country. The Christian Clerics did not voice out, saying any negative things against the military government that gave way to the civilian government.

Nigeria's Fourth Republic (May 29, 1999 - present): Nigeria completed a long and complex process that brought an end to military rule on May 29, 1999. At the Eagles' Square, Abuja, Abdul Salam Abu-bakar, the then Head of State and Commander in Chief of the Armed Forces of Nigeria, on May 29, 1999, handed over government to the democratically elected government, Chief Mathew Olusegun Okikiola Obasanjo of the Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) as Nigeria's Third Republic democratically elected president. However, Toyin Falola (2018) argues that the 1998-1999 election was full of irregularities, thus:

The election of 1998-1999 did not produce many peculiarities of its own, as the important variables that determined it had long existed: ethnicity, religion,

competition over resource sharing, minority and communal marginalization, personality and ego contests, and the prominent role of money.

President Obasanjo, in turn, handed the mantle of Nigerian leadership to President Shehu Yar'Adua, then followed by President Goodluck Jonathan, who gave the mantle of Nigerian leadership to Muhammadu Buhari, and President Muhammadu Buhari handed over to Bola Ahmed Tinubu as the current Nigerian democratically elected president of the All Progressive Congress (APC). However, the Fourth Republic was born during a period of significant economic decline, social decay, and widespread public cynicism and apathy (Falola, 2018). Presently, the eyes of Christian Clerics have opened, and they are campaigning for pastors to be involved in Nigeria's political governance, either by coming out to vote or being voted for. Some of the Nigerian Clerics that contested for political office include: Pastor Tunde Bakare of Latter Rain Assembly Ogba, Lagos; Pastor Oluyemi Oluleke Osinbajo of The Redeemed Church of God in Ikoyi, Lagos; Bishop Isaac Idahosa, the running mate of Rabiw Kwankwaso, the presidential candidate of New Nigeria Peoples Party (NNPC) during 2023 election, Rev. Fr. Ayacynth Iormem Allia, the APC governing candidate in Benue state and Usani Usani – a pastor in Cross River State and governorship candidate of Peoples Redemption Party (PRP) amongst others.

The introduction of democracy in Nigeria gave birth to a reign of terror as well as the shedding of innocent blood by individuals for personal gain. Elections were conducted poorly, with parties trying to outdo one another by every means. Rigging, arson, killing, beating, and confusion followed most political campaigns. Politicians looked for any means to get power. In agreement with this view, Falola submits that politicians seeking power consulted with traditional chiefs for support and visited “witch-doctors” in the middle of the night for magical power. Many in power relied on marabouts (Islamic charm makers) and traditional diviners to foretell their future and political fate, while chiefs sought the support of representatives from modern political institutions for financial gain, increased power, and improved access to the corridors of power (Falola, 2018). This has led to a low improvement in the welfare, lives, and properties of Nigerian citizens. This has also led the Youths to engage in all manners of vices such as prostitution, Cybercrime, ritual killing, kidnapping, and thuggery, amongst others. This ill-fated development has prompted Christian Clerics to speak out against these vices and advocate for Christian leaders who are guided by God to be elected as political leaders, aiming to bring about changes in society.

The way politics is practiced in modern times in Africa generally differs from how it used to be in colonial times. Politics is no longer a part-time concern. Many people enter politics without any Western educational qualifications for administrative jobs. So, if their party wins the election and they are given

important offices, by the next election, the fear of losing their position and going back to poverty causes some of them to indulge in corrupt practices. They utilize all available methods to maintain power. Because of the fear of going back to their former financial status, some of them engage in pagan practices to gain protection for their lives from poison, charms, occult powers, and bewitchment. This has led many politicians to join secret societies, including those who are Christians by name.

Christian Clerics and Political Governance

If Nigeria is to develop, Christian Clerics must take their rightful place in influencing the nation's governance spiritually, academically, socially, financially,, and even politically, to the glory of God and humanity. What is the role of Christian Church Priests in a situation like this in Nigeria? There are various proposed assumptions by many Christians that politics, by virtue of the way it is done in Nigeria, is a dirty game. Femi Olowonibi (2015, 126) observes that for a long time, Christian clerics viewed politics as an activity reserved for carnal or ungodly Christians, intended solely to prepare them for the kingdom of this world. In fact, many Missionary bodies and agencies discouraged their members from participating in politics and other “worldly” professions, such as joining the police and military forces, because of the imminence of the kingdom of God.

Politics in Nigeria has been characterised by various vices such as bribery, rigging, murder, violence, evil utterances, hooliganism, political assassination, God-Fatherism, oath-taking, among others. Until recent times, many Christians had no interest in partisan politics. Perhaps that is the reason the Church has not been much concerned with grooming Christians to represent the Church in Nigerian politics. Even today, some people think that no Christian should go for any political office, since it has become a do-or-die affair. Many politicians are willing to do whatever it takes to secure a particular office. The truth is that if you know what all these politicians are doing to get there, you will run (Enegho and Jesutunwase, 2020). Abodunrin (2017, p. 82) observes that the Church's role as a prophetic critic of society is neglected today. Instead, the chief emphasis of the Church is on the healing and prosperity ministry. Moreover, some of the few Christians who are involved in politics do so for selfish interests.

In a situation like this, the Christian Clergy in Nigeria should understand that preaching in the church is not enough to change Nigerian society. The Country needs to be led by good people who have zero tolerance for corruption. It is naive for a Christian to think that they can achieve much in the political community without being a partisan politician (Ezichi, 67). This is the right time for the Christian clerics to be involved in the political governance of Nigeria, because it would be a disservice to the Nigerian citizens if they allow unscrupulous men to

rule the Nation. It is a fact that Nigeria needs Christian clergy who have been appointed and anointed by God to occupy positions of political governance in this Country. The Christian Church in Nigeria should note that the involvement of Christian clerics in the nation's political governance will help right the wrongs of bad leaders.

Misconceptions Surrounding Christian Clergy Involvement in Politics

The misconceptions that hamper the level of Christian clerics' involvement in democratic governance in Nigeria include:

Lack of Theological Education in the Interpretation of Scriptures: 2 Corinthians 6:14 says, "Be not unequally yoked together with unbelievers: for what fellowship has righteousness with unrighteousness? Moreover, what communion has light with darkness?" This scripture serves as a guiding principle for many Nigerian Christian Clerics for justifying Christian apathy to political governance matters, as they see all that pertains to politics as having an unequal fellowship with unbelievers (Chioke). The meaning of this text is that St. Paul emphasises the need for believers to distance themselves from evil. He speaks of things that are so opposite that they cannot coexist. For instance, it is impossible to combine righteousness and wickedness, light and darkness, Christ and Belial, believer and unbeliever, the temple of God and idols. A choice must be made between these things.

Additionally, some Christian Clerics misinterpret Mathew 22:21, where Jesus said, "Render unto Caesar the things that are Caesar's and unto God the things that are God's," to mean that a faithful Christian ought not to mix their Christian life with Politics (Iordaah). However, the true meaning of this text is that Jesus Christ tackled the religious leaders' question by showing them that we have dual citizenship (1 Peter 2:17). Our citizenship in the nation requires that we pay money for the services and benefits we receive. In contrast, our citizenship in the kingdom of heaven requires that we pledge to God our ultimate obedience and commitment. (Life Application Bible, 1589). Lack of theological education leads to misinterpretation of the scriptures.

Lack of Unity in the Body of Christ: It is an undeniable fact that Christianity in Nigeria is a widely scattered family of denominations, all of them professing some faith in Christ, but that is not unique to Nigeria (Ayegboyin, 17). During the Apostolic era, in the earliest Christian Church, divisions existed within the Church, despite the absence of denominations. It should be recalled, as recorded in Acts Chapter 15 and Paul's stern letter to the Galatians, that there was serious division in the Apostolic Church. (Ayegboyin, 17). The interpretation of scriptures, discussion of creed, and Church politics resulted in the emergence of some dissenting groups. This illustrates the continuation of divisions within the Early Christian Church, which persists to this day.

Different Denominations in Nigeria: Some of the recognised denominations in Nigeria include Roman Catholics, mainline Protestant Congregations, Ethiopian or African Churches, indigenous African Movements, Pentecostals, Neo-Pentecostals (Ayeboyin, 18), and Third Generation Churches. With all these traditions of different beliefs and practices, one would describe Christians in Nigeria as a divided family with conflicting beliefs, doctrines, and attitudes. In agreement with this, Deji Ayeboyin (2000:18) says:

On the mission field, Protestants accused Catholics of Preaching man's word, instead of God's, indulging in the fetishism of medals. It is puzzling to hear a protestant minister remark that "Roman Catholics cannot be classified as Christians in the evangelistic service". As for the posture of the historic churches vis-à-vis the indigenous and the Neo-Pentecostal Churches, it is that of non-recognition. Mainline ministers describe the African Churches as nothing but Cults and the new Pentecostal Movements as "family business enterprises, sheep stealers, "cheap prosperity preachers". The Neo-Pentecostal Ministers, on the other hand, describe Mainline Churches as enfeebled and tottering organizations.

With all these differences, one wonders whether Christians can learn to get along with one another, emphasize their commonalities, and produce a candidate who will represent them in the political arena in Nigeria (Ephesians 4:15-16, 1 Corinthians 1:10).

Christian Clerics' Roles in the Political Governance of Nigeria

For Christian Church leaders to have influence on political governance in the Executive, Legislative, and Judicial arms of government in Nigeria, they must be involved. Toyin Falola (2018: 409) corroborates this fact and better expresses that religious leaders can speak to millions of people and shape their worldview and politics. The roles of the Christian Church Clergy in Nigeria's political governance are enormous. For instance, Malachi 2:6-7 says, "True instruction was in his mouth and nothing false was found on his lips. He walked with me in peace and uprightness, and turned many from sin. For the lips of a priest ought to preserve knowledge, because he is the messenger of the Lord Almighty and people seek instruction from his mouth"

The above text discusses the role of the priests during the dispensation of Prophet Malachi. The passive position of Christian Clerics to politics, while at the same time agitating for good governance, raises some critical questions, such as: on what justification are Christian clerics' cries, complaints, and condemnations of the people in power for failure to deliver, when power is left in the hands of the so-called people of dirty minds and acts? At this juncture, it is necessary to

explore ways the Christian Clerics in Nigeria can contribute to the political governance of Nigeria. In light of this, I would like to make the following suggestions:

Representation of Christ and His Church: The ministry of a priest is to represent Christ and His Church, particularly as pastor, prophet, evangelist, apostle or teacher of the word of God to the people; to share with the Leadership in the overseeing of the Church; to proclaim the Gospel; to administer the Sacrament; and to bless and declare pardon in the name of God. They are to carry out all the functions of a priest in the Pastoral office (Oyeku, 2015, 194). The description of what a priest should be did not fit the priests of Malachi's day. "Life and peace", "reverence," "true instruction", and "uprightness" were to be the hallmarks of those serving in the temple. There is no way to be no sign of falsehood on the lips and the ministry of turning many from sin. However, during Malachi's day, instead of turning people from sin, the priests were, by their words and deeds, turning them to sin (Iluno, 330). These are the kinds of things happening in the ministry of some Christian Clerics in Nigeria today.

In God's covenant with Israel, the Levites were given a special intercessory relationship with the people as ministers to God on behalf of the people. In this context, Levi represents all the Levitical Priests of Israel, who stood before God. Christian Clergy in Nigeria should stand in the gap between Nigerians and God, to know the mind of God concerning this Nation.

He Must Declare the Truth: The Levites were to be the teachers of the law. They were supposed to be an example of purity and obedience before the people, even to the devil. They were to exemplify in their lives the nature of the commandments of God. The Levites were tasked with administering justice and serving as peacemakers among the people. They were known for the truth that came out of their mouths (Baker and Kohlenberger, 1994, 1545). The Christian Clerics in this Country should run away from deceit, but always declare the truth. If the teachings of the Clergy are truthful, it will be effective. They would have exerted considerable impact on their members. The Church in our context should shine the light of ethical rectitude for the secular world to find the way to higher levels of transparency, accountability, and responsibility. In the management of its affairs, the spiritual ministry should exhibit the elevated values of trust, fairness, modesty, honesty, justice, equity, restraint, and fidelity. This is how it can claim moral superiority over the secular world.

He is the Messenger of the Lord: Through his teachings of the law of God to the people, the Leviticus Priest communicated the will of God to the people. Christian Clerics in Nigeria should communicate the will of God to the Nigerians. Malachi was God's messenger to the people (1:1), as was John the Baptist, who would be the messenger sent before the Messiah (3:1). As messengers of the Most High

God, both Malachi and John delivered to the people the message of God (Dickson, 1065). Therefore, Nigerian Christian Clerics should not be double-talk pastors. At all times, they must deliver to the people the mind and will of God in all situations and conditions.

The Lips of the Christian Clergy Must Keep Knowledge: The Priests are God's mouthpiece to their people, from whom they must receive instructions according to the lively oracles. Their lips should keep knowledge, not keep it from the people, but keep it for them. They must furnish themselves with knowledge and retain what they have got, that they may be like the good householder who brings out of his treasury things old and new. Not only in their heads, but also in their lips, must knowledge be kept; they must not only have it, but they must have it ready, must have it at hand, must have it at their tongue's end, to be communicated to others as the occasion arises (Dickson, 1065). Thus words of wisdom are on the lips of him who has understanding, with which they feed many (Prov. 10:13, 21). Wisdom to tell politicians that 'vanity upon vanity is vanity,' to run away from every form of bribery, corruption, embezzlement,, and other untoward attitudes (Eccl. 1:2).

The Christian Clergy Must Passionately Present the Gospel to Secure the People's Heart for Christ: A significant source of corruption in any form in Africa, generally, and Nigeria, to be specific, is wickedness from the heart that is ruled by the evil one. If Jesus Christ truly reigns in the hearts of Nigerians,, wicked thoughts and actions cannot be allowed. Emphasising this further, Henry (2011, 1268-1269) notes that,

He did turn many away from iniquity; he made it his business to do good, and God crowned his endeavors with tremendous success; he helped to save many a soul from death, and there are multitudes now in heaven blessing God that ever they knew him.

The Priests must lay themselves out to the utmost for the conversion of sinners. It is by the grace of God only that they can turn men from iniquity and yet can be said of a Pious laborious minister that he turned men from iniquity as a worker together with God. An instrument in his hand, and those that turn many to righteousness shall shine as stars (Dan.12:3). It should be noted that priests that are likely to turn men from iniquity are those that preach sound doctrine, live good lives and both according to the scripture; when the priest is upright many will be upright (Henry, 2011, 1268-1269). Do not forget that integrity as a Clergy Member does not depend on the prosperity of this world, but on how clearly you bring out "The Will of God" in whatever is happening around you and to you at a particular time.

The Preaching of the Kingdom: The preaching of the kingdom was the primary assignment of Jesus Christ, which the Early Christian Church continued. Instances include Peter at Pentecost in Acts 2:38; 3:19; Philip in Acts 8:12, Apostles Paul and Barnabas in Acts 14:22, and John the Revelator in Revelation 1:9, amongst others. The gospel message of these servants of God is for hearers to repent of their actions and to demonstrate their submission to the lordship of Jesus Christ and be saved from their generation's corrupt practices. The Christian Clerics should preach Jesus and let people understand that nobody can save them; only God can save us.

Salvation is not just of the soul but even that of the body. The primary purpose of Jesus Christ in his manifesto was deliverance from the bondage of sin, which ultimately led to political freedom in his time. This fact has been demonstrated in the history of the Church (Adekunle, 2019). In the early Church, the clergy were to some extent able to bring about some positive changes in society.

Fulfilment of Civic and Spiritual Responsibilities: It is the responsibility of Christian Clerics to ensure that the Church fulfils her civic and spiritual responsibilities to maintain relevance and shine as light in the world, since the church is domiciled on earth (Awojobi, 68). Like the ancient Prophets in Israel, the Christian Clerics are the watchdogs of the nation to speak on issues that threaten national security and the peaceful co-existence of the world in general and the Nigerian nation in particular.

Conclusion

The Christian Clerics in Nigeria have been given much, and much is required from them. Central to human development in a nation are security and good governance. Christian Clerics, as citizens of Nigeria, have the right and duty to participate in the political governance of this Nation, either to vote or be voted for. Religiously, Nigeria is a pluralistic society where burdens come in various shapes and sizes, and the standard of living is tough, tight, and life confounding. The Christian Clerics should also make the congregations politically aware, so that they will not dissociate Christianity from politics. He or she has a central role to play, because many of the causes of insecurity, kidnapping, and corruption are intensely spiritual. The source of bad political governance should thus be attacked at the roots, to reduce evil activities to the barest minimum in Nigeria. As Christian Clerics confront the forces of darkness head-on with the Word of Truth in their mouths and the Sword of the Spirit in their hands, they must be uncompromising. The Christian Clerics in Nigeria are the priests called and sent to fight corruption, insecurity, embezzlement, bribery, and kidnapping, amongst other things in Nigeria. They should be involved in the political governance of Nigeria, but only in a Christian manner, even at the grassroots level. The Christian Clerics in Nigeria should at this time mobilise members to participate in political

governance actively, avoid denominational divisions, and forge unity in all ramifications.

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